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Title:	CORRELATION BETWEEN SONOGRAPHY AND HISTOPATHOLOGY /FOLLOW UP RESCANS IN THE DIAGNOSES OF ADNEXAL MASSES IN A NIGERIAN POPULATION
Keyword:	
Description:	A THESIS SUBMITTED TO THE DEPARTMENT OF MEDICAL RADIOGRAPHY AND RADIOLOGICAL SCIENCES FACULTY OF HEALTH SCIENCES AND TECHNOLOGY. UNIVERSITY OF NIGERIA
Category:	MEDICAL RADIOGRAPHY AND
Publisher:	
Publication Date:	MAY, 2010
Signature:	Webmaster Digitally Signed by Webmaster's Name DN : CN = Webmaster's name O= University of Nigeria, Nsukka OU = Innovation Centre

**CORRELATION BETWEEN SONOGRAPHY AND HISTOPATHOLOGY / FOLLOW UP RESCANS IN
THE DIAGNOSES OF ADNEXAL MASSES IN A NIGERIAN POPULATION.**

M.Sc. DISSERTATION THESIS

**DEPARTMENT OF MEDICAL RADIOGRAPHY AND
RADIOLOGICAL SCIENCES**

BY

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SPECIALIZATION: MEDICAL IMAGING

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MAY, 2010

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TITLE OF DISSERTATION: Correlation between Sonography and Histopathology

/Follow Up Rescans in the Diagnoses of Adnexal Masses in A Nigerian Population.

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To my beloved mother Mrs. Patricia C. Okpaleke

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I was encouraged to embark on this study by my project supervisor Prof. (Mrs.) I.J.Okoye under whose close supervision, this work was completed. The example set by my former Head of Department, Dr. K. K. Agwu, in his understanding of teaching and research in Medical Radiography has been my greatest incentive throughout the period of this thesis. The present HOD, Mrs. F. Idigo has been of tremendous help as well.

My thanks goes to my immediate boss R.S.J. Babatunde (esq.), the Registrar/Chief Executive of the Radiographers Registration Board of Nigeria for his encouragement and support, and to my elder sister Miss Theresa Chinyere Okpaleke for her sponsorship.

I am indebted to Mr. Eze Charles for painstakingly going through the manuscript and offering useful advice and corrections. I must not forget Dr. Okaro, Mr Ochie Kalu and Mr. E. J. Akpan for their useful contributions.

I am grateful to the following staff of the Radiographers Registration Board of Nigeria; Mr. Oliver Amadi, Mrs. Tolu Alonge, Mr. Irodi Chidiebere and my friend Mr. Christian Onyekelu for their useful inputs.

I want to appreciate the excellent secretarial help of Mr. Sunday Adekoleoye and finally to my wife Ifeyinwa, words fail me to express my gratitude for her amazing continued support and tolerance.

M.S.Okpaleke.

ABSTRACT

Ultrasonography is the study of choice in the initial evaluation of suspected adnexal masses. The grey scale sonographic appearances of some adnexal masses overlap and may lead to erroneous diagnoses thereby limiting its diagnostic accuracy. This raises the query of the accuracy of grey scale sonography in providing precise diagnoses for adnexal masses. In addition, the sonography reports issued in most diagnostic centres in Nigeria are not routinely followed up by the sonographer/sonologist to confirm their diagnostic accuracy. The main objective of the study is to match definitive sonography diagnoses with histopathology diagnoses and serial rescans in order to evaluate the accuracy of sonography as a diagnostic tool for adnexal masses. The secondary objective is to characterize the commonly occurring adnexal masses in the study population. Features identified will serve as a useful guide to sonographers and sonologists for characterizing adnexal masses in Nigeria. In this prospective study, commonly occurring adnexal masses in the population were characterized sonographically in 392 subjects aged between 5 years and 65 years from referrals to the Radiology department of Eko Hospitals, in Lagos State, using standard techniques. Each subject was followed up with the referring gynaecologist/physician to document the management procedure that was embarked upon by the clinical team. One hundred and seventy two (44%) subjects had laparotomy, excision of the mass, and histopathological diagnoses of their masses and 220 subjects who did not require surgery were followed up with serial rescans. Out of the 172 subjects that went for laparotomy, 136 (79%) had histopathology diagnoses that matched with initial sonography diagnoses ($r = 0.93$). Out of the 220 subjects that underwent follow up rescans, 212 (96%) had rescan diagnoses that matched initial sonography diagnoses ($r = 0.99$). Three hundred and forty eight (89%) out of the 392 subjects that underwent laparotomy / follow up rescans had histopathology / follow up rescan diagnoses that matched initial sonography diagnoses { $r = 0.99$, accuracy (92%), sensitivity (88%), specificity (92%), PPV (49%) and NPV (99%)} while initial sonography diagnoses were erroneous in 44 (11%) subjects. A regression model for predicting the accuracy of sonography diagnoses is given by $Y = 0.941x - 2.340$ ($r^2 = 0.983$, $p < 0.05$). There was no statistically significant difference between sonography and histopathology diagnoses / follow up rescans noted ($\chi^2 = 3.56$, $\chi^2_{0.05} = 5.991$, $p > 0.05$). Benign adnexal masses were common in the study population as they constituted 92% of all identified adnexal masses and were predominantly among premenopausal subjects between 35 and 44 years. They include functional cysts (44%), benign ovarian masses (21%), hydrosalpinx, pyosalpinx and tubo-ovarian abscesses resulting from pelvic inflammatory diseases (10%). The study concludes that grey scale sonography is valuable in the diagnoses of adnexal masses.

Table of Content	page
Title page	i
Approval page	ii
Dedication	iii
Acknowledgement	iv
Abstract	v
CHAPTER ONE	
Background of the Study	1
1.1 Introduction	1
1.2 Statement of Problem	7
1.3 Hypothesis	7
1.4 Purpose of study	8
1.5 Significance of study	8
1.6 Scope of the study	8
1.7 Limitations of study	9
CHAPTER TWO	
2.1 Literature review	10
CHAPTER THREE	
3.0 Diagnosis and Management of Adnexal Masses	21
3.1 Types of Adnexal Masses	21

3.2	Single Cystic Masses	21
3.3	Multiple Cystic Masses	24
3.4	Complex Masses	25
3.5	Solid Masses	27
3.6	Ultrasound Evaluation of Adnexal Masses	27
3.7	Management of Adnexal Masses	28
CHAPTER FOUR		
	Research Methodology	31
4.1	Research design	31
4.2	Population	31
4.21	Inclusion Criteria	31
4.22	Exclusion Criteria	32
4.3	Sample Size	32
4.4	Sampling procedure	32
4.5	Equipment used	33
4.6	Data Collection	33
4.7	Scanning Technique	33
4.71	Images	35-38
4.8	Data Analysis	39
4.81	Table of signal detection theory	40

4.82 Table showing signal detection theory values for sonography	
Diagnoses and histopathology diagnoses only	40
4.83 Formulae	40
4.9 Comments on result	41
4.91 List of Tables	46
4.92 List of Figures	47
4.93 Tests of hypothesis	63
CHAPTER FIVE	
5.0 Discussion & Conclusion	64
5.1 Discussion	64
5.12 Accuracy of sonography in the Diagnoses of adnexal masses.	64
5.13 Patterns of occurrence of the adnexal masses	70
5.2 Conclusion	72
5.3 Areas of further Research	72
References	73-85
Appendix	

CHAPTER ONE

BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

1.1 INTRODUCTION

The Adnexae refers to the region within the female pelvis that contains the ovary, fallopian tube, round ligament and structures arising from associated embryonic rests. This area may also be involved in pathology related to the uterus, bowel, retroperitoneum, or metastatic disease from another site such as breast or stomach.

Masses can be found in the adnexae of females of all ages from fetuses to the elderly which may either be symptomatic, or discovered incidentally. While some will regress spontaneously; others may require a surgical procedure for histologic diagnoses and treatment. Diagnostic clues to determine the etiology can be obtained from the history, physical examination, findings from imaging studies and results of laboratory tests.

Common adnexal masses are classified as cystic, complex or solid masses. Common cystic masses include follicular cysts, corpus luteum cyst, cystic teratomas, paraovarian cyst, and hydrosalpinx. Complex masses are mainly cystadenomas (serous or mucinous), haemorrhagic cyst, endometrioma, ectopic pregnancy, teratoma (dermoid), abscess, hydrosalpinx. Adenocarcinomas, solid teratomas, arrhenoblastomas, fibromas and dysgerminomas are examples of solid masses (Roger et al., 2007; Douglas et al., 2010).

The reported prevalence of ovarian neoplasm varies widely depending upon the

population studied. Approximately 289,000 women are hospitalized annually in the United States because of ovarian neoplasms and even greater numbers are found to have adnexal or pelvic masses during routine physical examination or during evaluation for other complaints (Cutin, 1994). Ovarian cancer remains the fourth leading cause of death among American women (Landis, 1998). In Lagos state (South-west Nigeria), oral discussion with sonographers and sonologists suggest that majority of the patients referred to the ultrasound departments at the Eko Hospitals for Pelvic scan present with different kinds of adnexal disorders including adnexal malignancies. This triggered off my curiosity to investigate the accuracy of sonography in the diagnoses of adnexal masses.

Other imaging modalities used to evaluate the adnexae include; Computed Tomography (CT), Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) and Positron Emission Tomography (PET). CT has been used primarily for patients with ovarian malignancies, either to assess disease extent prior to surgery or as a substitute for confirmatory laparotomy.

CT of the abdomen or pelvis allows comprehensive evaluation of all potential sites of peritoneal implants or lymphadenopathy, as well as the primary tumour site. CT also allows use of oral contrast agents to distend and mark the bowel and help differentiate bowel from peritoneal implants. This gives this modality a major advantage over ultrasound and MRI. For these reasons, CT is a very effective

method of evaluating the extent of the disease in women with ovarian malignancy.

However, available studies have shown that CT is neither specific enough to replace laparotomy or even percutaneous biopsy (Prayer et al., 1993) nor significantly superior to other imaging modalities in staging ovarian malignancy (Forstner et al., 1995). A few studies have suggested that MRI particularly gadolinium enhanced, fat saturated breath-hold techniques, may be more accurate than CT in staging ovarian carcinoma (Forstner et al., 1995) because it combines some of the best features of CT and Ultrasound. On the contrary, another extensive study that compared Ultrasound, CT and MRI in the staging of ovarian malignancy noted little difference between the modalities. (Kurtz et al., 1999)

Furthermore, CT may play a useful role in diagnosing adnexal masses, but it is not indicated for the differential diagnosis of adnexal masses because of risk of radiation exposure and poor soft tissue discrimination except when identification of fat and calcifications is important to make the diagnosis (Bohm-valez et al., 2005). Thus, the risk of radiation exposure involved in C.T is a disadvantage compared to US and MRI (Bohm – Valez et al., 2005)

Inspite of the relative advantages of MRI and CT over Ultrasound, ultrasonography remains the study of choice in the initial evaluation of suspected adnexal masses because it is relatively inexpensive and widely available. Transabdominal ultrasound (TAS), transvaginal ultrasound (TAS) or both should be performed for

the evaluation of adnexal masses (Roger et al., 2007). Numerous studies have interrogated the issue of grey – scale criteria being capable of differentiating between benign and malignant ovarian masses. Ultrasound, whether transabdominal or endovaginal, relies on morphologic assessment of the tumor to distinguish between benign and malignant disease. Morphologic features such as; thick, irregular walls and septa, papillary projections, and solid, moderately echogenic loculi, have been described as suggestive of malignant tumor (Douglas et al., 2010). Other morphologic scoring systems have been proposed and are based on the wall thickness, inner wall structure, septal characteristics, and echogenicity of the lesion (Yong-yeon et al., 2000).The advent of high frequency endovaginal probes allowed high resolution imaging of pelvic organs in general and of the ovaries in particular. Endovaginal ultrasonography (US) is the most practical modality for assessment of ovarian tumors because it is readily available and has a high negative predictive value (Yong-yeon et al., 2000).This finding is supported by a related study which stated that Endovaginal Ultrasound has allowed markedly improved resolution for uterine and adnexal imaging and is essential for imaging adnexal masses whose nature is not clearly demonstrable using transabdominal Ultrasound (Sassone et al., 1991).The later study developed a morphologic scoring system that demonstrated a sensitivity of 100% and specificity of 83% in distinguishing between benign and malignant ovarian masses.

Reliable differentiation of benign from malignant adnexal masses cannot be obtained by TAS or TVS alone because of relatively high false positive rate in complex masses (Ferrazzi et al., 1997).

Color Doppler Ultrasound of ovarian masses helps identify vascularized tissue and can assist in differentiating solid tumor tissue from nonvascularized structures in complex adnexal masses. It is also used in conjunction with pulsed Doppler ultrasound to identify vessels for waveform analysis. Most studies have relied on waveform analysis to distinguish benign from malignant ovarian masses, but more information can be obtained with color Doppler Ultrasound (Kurjack et al., 1992). Benign lesions tend to initiate new tumor blood vessel formation peripherally from pre-existing host vessels, whereas malignant tumors tend to initiate new tumor blood vessel formation centrally (Dock et al., 1991). Waveform analysis is based on the fact that malignant tumor vessels are morphologically abnormal (Reles et al., 1997): they lack smooth muscle in their walls and demonstrate an irregular course and arteriovenous shunt formation (Kurjack et al., 1992). In addition, malignant tumor vessels generally have low impedance, which causes high diastolic flow and low systolic-diastolic variation. Some differentiation between benign and malignant masses is achieved by quantifying these differences.

Moreover, two indices have been used in analyzing Doppler waveforms: the pulsatility index and the resistive index. Both increase with increasing distal

vascular resistance, and the two indexes have a high correlation. Resistive indexes less than 0.4–0.8 and pulsatility indexes less than 1.0 are generally considered to be suspicious for malignancy (Hamper et al., 1993). Doppler Ultrasound yields variable results in distinguishing benign from malignant masses, with a sensitivity of 50%–100% and a specificity of 46%–100% (Hata et al., 1992). Differing results are partly due to varying threshold values and corresponding tradeoffs between sensitivity and specificity (Yong-yeon et al., 2000).

Adnexal masses have a long list of diagnostic possibilities and should be correlated with history and laparotomy tests (Bohm-velez et al., 2005). Histopathology and laparotomy are important gold standards used to confirm the result of ultrasound diagnoses (Eugene et al., 2001). Several studies have compared ultrasound results with histopathology tests/follow up rescans. In a study to assess the value of ultrasonography in the diagnoses of adnexal masses, a positive correlation between the result of ultrasonographic diagnoses with histopathologic diagnoses and follow up examinations when surgery was not indicated was obtained in 74.6% of the patients studied (Satoska et al., 1991). A higher diagnostic accuracy of 87.3% had been obtained in a related study to evaluate the accuracy, sensitivity and specificity of combined clinical assessment, grey scale abdominal ultrasound and serum CA 125 assay in predicting malignant status of pelvic masses (Eugene et al., 2001).

From the available literature and to the best of our knowledge there is no documented study on the accuracy of ultrasound diagnoses of adnexal masses in Nigeria. This study is therefore aimed at establishing the accuracy of ultrasound diagnoses by correlating ultrasound findings with histopathology results and serial rescans. Since ultrasonography is the more commonly available in Nigeria, establishing that it is indeed efficient in the evaluation of adnexal masses would add confidence to management decisions which are often dependant on this sole modality.

It is hoped that this study will provide a useful guide that can be used by sonographers and sonologists for assessing adnexal masses and emphasize the need for closer interaction between the diagnostic imaging department and the other disciplines in managing patients with adnexal masses.

1.2 STATEMENT OF PROBLEMS

Though sonographic features that enable distinction between benign and malignant masses are subtle, most ultrasound reports issued in many ultrasound centers in Nigeria especially in Lagos state are not routinely followed up to outcome by the sonographer/sonologist to confirm the accuracy of their predictive diagnoses.

1.3 HYPOTHESIS

H₀: There is no significant difference between the sonographic diagnosis of adnexal pathology and the definitive diagnosis provided by histopathology / follow

up rescans.

H₁: There is a significant difference between the sonographic diagnoses of adnexal pathology and the definitive diagnosis provided by histopathology / follow up rescans.

1.4 PURPOSE OF STUDY

The main objectives of this study are:

1. To establish the diagnostic accuracy of ultrasonography in the diagnoses of adnexal masses by correlating sonographic findings with their histopathology reports and follow up rescan.
2. To identify the pattern of occurrence of varying adnexal masses amongst patients who have been referred for sonography.

1.5 SIGNIFICANCE OF STUDY

It is hoped that this study will act as a useful guide that can be used by sonographers and sonologists for assessing adnexal masses in Nigeria. It will also emphasize the need for closer interaction between the imaging department and other disciplines in managing patients with adnexal masses.

1.6 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

This study was done at the Radiology department of Eko Hospitals in Lagos state

of Nigeria.

1.7 LIMITATIONS OF STUDY

Patient's refusal to undergo trans-vaginal sonography even when clinically indicated was a major setback. Lack of Doppler/colour flow facility and 3-D ultrasound equipment at the study centres introduced difficulties in characterizing the adnexal masses further in addition to paucity of funds.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

An ultrasound examination is the most valuable diagnostic study in the evaluation of an adnexal or pelvic mass and has been found clinically useful in characterizing adnexal masses (Eze et al., 2009). To evaluate the adnexae, both transvaginal and transabdominal techniques are important (Roger et al., 2007). Compared with transabdominal pelvic ultrasonography, transvaginal ultrasonography provides improved resolution for visualization of female pelvic organs, with less artifact and has superseded the transabdominal approach in many situations (Weissman 1996). Transvaginal sonography has also been reported to be more discriminatory in providing precise specific diagnoses of non – malignant ovarian masses (Pelusi et al., 1996; Ifene 2000) and accurate in the differentiation between non-malignant and malignant ovarian abnormalities (De kroon et al., 2004).

Despite the expanding role of transvaginal sonography in routine gynecologic examination as well as screening for ovarian cancer, problems using TVS for detecting ovarian masses and visualizing the ovaries in postmenopausal women has been reported (DiSantis et al., 1993). The later study was designed prospectively to assess the capability of TVS in evaluating the ovary and detecting adnexal masses. TVS was used to examine 113 ovaries in 59 women within 72hrs before gynecologic surgery. Ovarian size and echotexture were assessed and a search was made for adnexal masses. Sonograms were interpreted without

knowledge of the clinical history or results of physical examination and the sonographic findings were compared with surgical and pathologic data. The results revealed that in 22 premenopausal patients, 16 (72%) of 21 histologically normal ovaries were identified on sonograms, but only 13 (59%) of 22 adnexal masses. Lesions as large as 177cm³ were not detected. In the 37 postmenopausal patients, 12 (20%) of 59 normal ovaries and 6 (54%) of 11 adnexal masses were identified. 5 malignant masses (largest 113cm³) were not detected. The study concluded that the ability of TVS to detect normal postmenopausal ovaries and ovarian masses were suboptimal in a number of cases and advised practitioners to be aware of these limitations. Other related studies have also cautioned that the major concern about TVS screening for ovarian cancer is its relatively low positive predictive value (Van Nagell et al., 1991; Kupesic, 2006). In addition, a completely reliable differentiation of benign from malignant masses cannot be obtained by TAS or TVS alone because of relatively high false positive rate in complex masses (Ferrazzi et al., 1997). As a result Transvaginal colour and pulsed Doppler sonography were introduced into clinical practice in an attempt to decrease the false positive rate of morphologic sonographic adnexal masses (Juan et al., 2007).

Doppler examination is performed when any abnormality of the ovary including a cyst is detected. Pulsed Doppler interrogation of the adnexal branch of the uterine artery, the ovarian artery, or intratumoral flow is performed to determine the

resistive index [(RI) = systolic - diastolic/systolic] or pulsatility index [(PI) = systolic - diastolic/mean)]. Patients with normal menstrual cycles are best scanned in the first 10 days of the cycle; this avoids confusion with normal changes in intraovarian blood flow, since high diastolic flow occurs in the luteal phase around the corpus luteum (Shimizu et al., 1990). A debate in literature exists regarding the value of a resistive index in distinguishing between benign and malignant adnexal masses. Some scholars used a cutoff of greater than 0.4 as a normal RI in a nonfunctioning ovary (Kurjak et al., 1991) while other investigators employ a PI of greater than 1 as normal (Fleischer et al., 1992). Intratumoral vessels, low-resistance flow, and absence of a normal diastolic notch in the Doppler waveform are all signs that are worrisome for malignancy (Fleischer et al., 1992). Unfortunately, abnormal waveforms can also be seen in inflammatory masses, metabolically active masses (including ectopic pregnancy), and corpus luteum cysts (Fleischer et al., 1991). Other Problems associated with Doppler ultrasound include operator dependence and unavailability of established standard criteria in distinguishing benign from malignant waveforms. It is also difficult to detect signal for waveform analysis in adnexal masses that lack septations, papillae and solid areas. In premenopausal women, physiologic alterations in the ovary due to the menstrual cycle can result in lowered blood vessel resistance mimicking malignancy and thus abnormal

doppler indexes that could be misleading. This has been collaborated by a related study which opined that the use of resistive index might improve specificity in the assessment of possible malignant adnexal lesion but cannot be relied upon as a parameter (Levine et al., 1994). As a result, the use of Transvaginal colour and pulsed Doppler sonography in characterizing adnexal masses based on tumour vascularization has been found to be poorly reproducible (Juan et al., 2007)

A simpler approach based on morphologic sonographic assessment and tumour vessel distribution using colour or power Doppler sonography has been proposed (Guerriero et al., 2002). This approach has proved very useful for discriminating benign from malignant adnexal tumours because the probability of malignancy is high in complex adnexal masses with central vessel distribution whereas complex masses without vessel distribution or peripheral blood flow are usually benign.

Also, the usefulness of colour Doppler sonography in the differential diagnosis of adnexal masses has been reported to produce a sensitivity of 100% when its predictivity for differentiating various adnexal masses was correlated with histopathological data (Caruso et al., 1998). On the contrary, a comparative study of transvaginal colour sonography and conventional sonography in the pre – operative assessment of adnexal masses yielded lower sensitivity of 80% and specificity of 67% using colour Doppler sonography in premenopausal patients whereas in

postmenopausal patients, the sensitivity and specificity were 93% and 83% respectively (Reles et al., 1997). Higher specificities of 95% has been reported by similar studies (Reiber et al., 2001)

Moreover, the use of a combination of morphologic analysis with endovaginal ultrasound and pulsed Doppler waveform analysis with color Doppler ultrasound has been proven to afford better differentiation of benign and malignant ovarian masses than would use of either procedure alone (Timor – Tritch et al., 1993).

TABLE I
MORPHOLOGICAL SCORING SYSTEM

S/N	SCORING CRITERIA	SCORE
1.	Smooth/small irregular wall structures with shadowing and thin or no septa	0
2.	Thick septa/without shadowing	1
3.	Solid walls	2
4.	Walls with papillary projection	3

Adapted from Timor-Tritch et al., (1993)

The morphological scoring system (Table I above) used showed that adnexal masses with smooth or small irregular wall structures scored zero while those with solid walls or papillary projections on their walls scored 2 or 3 respectively. On the

other hand, Adnexal masses with shadowing/thin or no septa also scored zero while those with thick septa/without shadowing scored 1. Their morphologic scoring system yielded a sensitivity of 94%, a specificity of 87%, and a disappointing positive predictive value of 60%. When the pulsatility index or resistance index was included, more acceptable levels of sensitivity (94%), specificity (99%), and positive predictive value (94%) were obtained. The later findings has been collaborated by another related study which proposed the combined use of B-mode ultrasound with colour and spectral Doppler as the first and foremost diagnostic modality for patients with adnexal masses as it will go a long way in establishing an early and definite diagnosis of ovarian malignancy (Taori et al., 2002). The later study used spectral Doppler to asses the nature of blood vessels picked up on colour Doppler to obtain diagnostic result in 96.29% of malignant tumours (pulsatility index < 0.8 in contrast to only 6.06% of benign tumours). However, there were still some benign tumours that showed a complex appearance with central vessel distribution such as cystadenofibromas, mucinous cystadenomas, tubo-ovarian abscesses, and solid ovarian benign tumours such as Brenner tumours, granulosa cell tumours and ovarian fibroma which are very difficult to discriminate from ovarian malignancies using colour or power Doppler sonography (Juan et al., 2007). Some fibriod have also been reported to have high diastolic arterial waveforms similar to some ovarian cancers (Okoye et al., 2000).

As a result, two-dimensional color Doppler sonography has been reported to provide only a subjective estimation of uterine and ovarian vascularity and is limited by providing flow depiction in a single plane as opposed to the sample volume as obtained by three-dimensional imaging.

Therefore, to overcome the limitations of conventional two dimensional (2D) sonography, three Dimensional sonography emerged as one of the most important recent advances in pelvic ultrasonography and an accurate imaging modality for the evaluation of the adnexae (Nick, 2005). Three-dimensional sonography allows the simultaneous assessment of individual sectional planes, which dependent upon the particular field of interest may be examined in one of several different viewing modalities to maximise the information available and improve spatial awareness (King et al., 1990; Brunner et al., 1995). Uniquely, three-dimensional sonography allows demonstration of the coronal plane perpendicular to the transducer face facilitating the identification of surface irregularities which can then be accounted for during volume measurement (Maymon et al., 2000). The digital technology central to its development also means that three-dimensional imaging lends itself to telemedicine, as it allows the storage of large datasets without loss of information that may be subsequently analysed off-line and reappraised by experts in a 'virtual real-time consultation' (Heer et al., 2001). Advocates of three-dimensional sonography suggest that these features offer the user the following advantages in

comparison to two-dimensional sonography including reduced scanning times that will offer more cost-effective use of equipment and sonographer time (Pretorius et al.,1995).Other benefits of three-dimensional ultrasound according to the later study include allowing the physician: to evaluate arbitrary planes not available with two-dimensional ultrasound due to patient body habitus; to measure organ dimensions and volumes; to obtain anatomic and blood flow information; to improve assessment of complex anatomic anomalies; to confirm normalcy; to standardized the ultrasound exam procedures; to enhance the understanding of physicians in primary care facilities and communicate volume data over networks for consultation at tertiary facilities. Comparison of 2D ultrasound with 3D ultrasound in related study found that 3D ultrasonound has a significantly higher specificity ($P < 0.005$), accuracy ($P < 0.001$), and significantly lower false positive rate ($P < 0.005$) than 2D ultrasound (Toshiyiki et al, 1999). The study also suggested that 3D ultrasound might be a better means of differentiating between malignant and benign ovarian tumours. This findings is supported by another related study which also compared 2D ultrasound with 3D power Doppler imaging and used histopathological diagnoses following surgical exploration to confirm the sonography findings (Cohen et al., 2001). Sonographic criteria used in the later study for diagnosing ovarian cancer were based on a system that included morphological characteristics, histologic prediction and power Doppler imaging.

The result showed that two dimensional grey scale ultrasound identified 56% of the masses as suspicious for cancer including all malignancies yielding a sensitivity, specificity and positive predictive value of 100%, 54%, and 35% respectively. However evaluation with 3D power Doppler identified only 39% cases as suspicious (including all malignant cases) resulting in a sensitivity, specificity and positive predictive value of 100%, 75%, and 50% respectively. The study concluded that 3D power Doppler imaging better defines the morphological and vascular characteristics of ovarian lesions. All malignancies were correctly identified by both 2D and 3D imaging although the specificity improved with the addition of 3D Power Doppler. This improved diagnostic accuracy may promote improved patient care by separating complex benign masses from ovarian cancer, therefore facilitating physician referral (Cohen et al., 2001).

Furthermore, contrast enhanced, three-dimensional power Doppler sonography has been reported to be better than three-dimensional power Doppler in the differentiation of benign and malignant adnexal lesions (kupesic, 2000). In the later study, 45 subjects with complex adnexal lesions of uncertain malignancy at transvaginal B mode and/ or Colour Doppler Sonography were evaluated prospectively with three-dimensional power Doppler sonography before and after injection of contrast agent. Presence of a penetrating pattern and a mixed penetrating and peripheral pattern suggested adnexal malignancy. All the results

were compared with histopathology. Contrast enhanced 3-Dimensional Power Doppler detected all cases of malignancies by displaying mixed penetrating and peripheral patterns on scan but misdiagnosed few benign masses as malignant which had earlier been detected by unenhanced 3- Dimensional power Doppler modality. The use of a contrast agent with three-dimensional power Doppler sonography showed diagnostic efficiency of 95.6% that was superior to that of nonenhanced three-dimensional power Doppler sonography (86.7%). The study concluded that contrast-enhanced, three-dimensional power Doppler sonography provides better visualization of tumor vascularity in complex adnexal masses and if used together with three-dimensional morphologic ultrasound assessment, might precisely discriminate benign from malignant adnexal lesions. The conclusion of the later study has been collaborated by another related study (Henri marret et al., 2004).

In addition, recent studies also suggest that statistically derived scoring systems or predictors based on logistic regression analysis (Dirk et al., 2005), three dimensional power Doppler vascular network assessment of adnexal masses (Juan et al.,2008) and the risk of malignancy index (Geomini et al.,2009) are also useful like contrast enhanced power doppler sonography in the correct diagnoses of adnexal masses.

Nevertheless, both conventional and Doppler ultrasound are less accurate than MRI

in diagnosing ovarian malignancy (Kurtz et al., 1999) because sonography is limited in its range of tissue characterization and field of view unlike MRI (susanna, 2006). MRI can be used definitely to characterize fat, blood, simple fluid and the enhancement properties of solid tissues can be measured with the administration of Gadolinium. The later study also affirms that adnexal lesions suspected to be benign on sonography should be referred to MRI for further evaluation and in most cases for definitive characterization. On the other hand, it is impracticable to perform MRI of all suspected adnexal lesions because MRI is less accessible than sonography, hence this modality is reserved for equivocal cases.

Unfortunately, Doppler Ultrasound and MRI are emerging imaging modalities that are not easily available in most of the diagnostic centers across the country. As a result, most physicians in Nigeria especially in Lagos State, rely on grey scale sonographic findings to manage patients with suspected adnexal masses. It is disturbing to note that these sonographic findings were rarely followed up to confirm their accuracy. Hence this study is aimed at establishing the accuracy of sonography in the diagnoses of adnexal masses by correlating sonographic findings with histopathology diagnoses and follow up rescans.

CHAPTER THREE

3.0 DIAGNOSIS AND MANAGEMENT OF ADNEXAL MASSES

3.1 TYPES OF ADNEXAL MASSES

Adnexal masses are divided into four basic groups namely:

1. Single Cystic Masses
2. Multiple Cystic Masses
3. Complex Masses and
4. Solid Masses.

3.2 SINGLE CYSTIC MASSES:

They have well defined smooth borders and show good through transmission and are usually spherical. They can be within the ovary (intra-ovarian) or outside the ovary (extra ovarian).

Intraovarian Single Cystic Masses.

- i. **Follicular Cysts:** They are caused by continued hormonal stimulation of a follicle that does not rupture at ovulation. They are usually small but may measure up to 10cm. Ninety five percent (95%) of functional cysts disappear after the next menstruation cycle. Occasionally, simple ovarian cysts may cause a problem by delaying menstruation, rupturing, twisting and causing pain. Haemorrhage may occur within a follicular cyst and cause internal echoes although they are generally echo free.

- ii. **Corpus Luteum Cyst**: They are caused by Human Chorionic Gonadotropin (HCG) stimulation in pregnancy. They may grow and reach a size of 10cm. They usually disappear before 20weeks of pregnancy.
- iii. **Serous Cystadenoma**: They are the commonest benign tumors of the ovary. They are large, thin walled and may have septa within them. They may be large and often times grow enough to occupy most of the abdomen.
- iv. **Endometrioma**: Fluid mass that contains internal echoes in a patient without the clinical features of pelvic inflammatory disease. Endometriosis is a common condition in which functioning endometrial tissue is present within or outside the uterus. Usually ectopic tissues is found on the ovaries, the external surface of uterus or scattered over the peritoneum (especially in the dependent parts of the pelvis). The endometrial tissue cyclically bleeds and proliferates in diffuse form, this leads to disorganization of the pelvic anatomy with an appearance similar to pelvic inflammatory disease or ectopic pregnancy.
- v. **Dermoid**: This is the most common germ cell tumour. The tumour has been found in young children although it occurs in women of child bearing age. Clinical findings include abdominal mass and or pain secondary to torsion or haemorrhage. This tumour is unilateral. Teeth, bones and fat can be seen on plain films.

- vi. **Cystadenocarcinoma**: Cystadenocarcinoma may occur within the ovary. They are generally not entirely cystic. It may contain echogenic material within the cyst eroding through the cyst wall.

Extraovarian cystic masses:

- i. **Paraovarian cysts** – they lie between the uterus and the ovary. These cysts are remnants of the wolffian duct that lies parallel to the upper third of the vagina, uterus and fallopian tubes. Patients are asymptomatic when the paraovarian cysts are small and non-tender, but the cyst may become large with extension into the upper abdomen. The cysts can arise anywhere in the adnexal structures; when they fill the pelvis, their point of origin may not be clear. Their size does not change with the hormonal cycle.
- ii. **Peritoneal Inclusion Cyst**: Peritoneal inclusion cysts are a consequence of previous surgery or infection. The peritoneal surfaces become abcesced and fluid slowly collects. These cysts may be of any shape and may contain septa.
- iii. **Endometrioma**: Features are same as described above (intraovarian masses) except that the ectopic endometrial tissue occurs outside the ovary.
- iv. **Hydrosalpinx**: Hydrosalpinx may be a sequel of pelvic inflammatory disease or any infection involving the fallopian tube. The pus in a pyosalpinx resorbs and is transformed into fluid. The sonographic finding may suggest hydrosalpinx when the tube folds over on itself and forms a funnel shaped or

kinked structure.

3.3 **MULTIPLE CYSTIC MASSES:**

- i. Endometriosis. A disease state that occurs during the reproductive years.

Endometriosis is caused by implantation of endometrial tissue in abnormal locations in the pelvis. This ectopic endometrial tissue responds to cyclic ovarian hormones and bleeds as if it were located within the uterus. Endometrial cysts (endometrioma) may develop in these areas of bleeding. Small cysts are termed 'blebs' whereas larger ones, because of their contents (blood) and colour, are called chocolate 'cysts'. This type of cyst may occur singly, but more than one are generally seen. Because these cysts contain blood, they may contain internal echoes in the form of either many low-level echogenic structures or a dense echogenic "blob"

- ii. **Theca Lutein Cysts:** Theca lutein cysts are usually seen in conjunction with trophoblastic disease such as hydatidiform mole and choriocarcinoma. They form as a response to the abnormally high levels of HCG that are present in trophoblastic disease. They may become very large, have several septa, and are generally bilateral. Similar cysts are associated with drugs given for infertility (e.g. Pergonal), in which case they are known as hyperstimulation cysts.

- iii. **Tubo-Ovarian Abscesses:** Tubo-ovarian abscesses are irregularly shaped,

thick walled, fluid-filled structures in the adnexa that may develop a few internal echoes and even an internal fluid-fluid level. Tubo-ovarian abscesses are usually bilateral, but occasionally a unilateral lesion is seen. These abscesses are usually not an isolated finding; multiple abscesses are often noted elsewhere.

- iv. **Pyosalpinx**: Pyosalpinx are dilated, pus-filled fallopian tubes. Pyosalpinx have a tubular configuration that may be recognizable only when an endovaginal transducer is used. Internal echoes are generally present when the tube is pus filled. The tube walls are thickened and irregular.

3.4 COMPLEX MASSES

1. COMPLEX MASSES IN THE OVARY

Complex masses in the ovary contain sonolucent and echogenic areas. The walls are generally smooth; the shape is usually spherical.

- i. ***Mucinous Cystadenoma and Cystadenocarcinoma of the Ovary.***

Mucinous cystadenoma and cystadenocarcinoma of the ovary are ovarian masses of the reproductive or postmenopausal age group which are less common than the serous type. A spherical cystic mass is present with many septa, and there is some solid material within the septa. When benign, the margins are usually well defined. Malignancy is

suggested by large masses of solid tissue and ill-defined borders.

Benign and malignant mucinous tumours may be associated with free peritoneal fluid, but the presence of ascites favours malignancy.

ii. ***Cystic Teratomas (Dermoids)***. Cystic teratomas, cysts of the reproductive or premenarche age group, have a wide variety of sonographic appearances:

- a) Mainly cystic. These often have an echogenic area with acoustic shadowing due to calcium. Teeth may be seen on a radiograph.
- b) Complex Internal Structure. These are echogenic areas from fat, hair or bone, often with areas of shadowing. Fluid – fluid level may be seen
- c) “Iceberg” appearance. Often the echogenic material within the cysts shadows the main bulk of the lesion, rendering the mass invisible.
- d) Echogenic mass. The echogenic mass may blend in with neighbouring bowel, but the lesion’s presence will be revealed by an indentation of the bladder or will be seen on endovaginal ultrasound.

iii. **Ovarian Cancer**. Ovarian cancer is one of the leading causes of death in women. An absolute diagnosis of malignancy cannot usually be made sonographically. However, several ultrasound features are strongly suggestive:

1. Poor definition of the lesion’s borders due to tumour spread to adjacent

organs

2. Bizarre, complex appearance.
3. “Malignant” ascites – loculated fluid between fixed loops of bowel with peritoneal metastases
4. Solid areas within a cystic complex.
5. Bilateral nature.

3.5 SOLID MASSES

Solid masses contain only low-level echoes, show little or no through transmission, and have irregular or smooth walls.

i. Ovarian Masses

If a solid mass of the ovary is recognized sonographically, most often a specific diagnosis cannot be made. Nevertheless, the features of malignancy, as described previously, should be sought. Any solid ovarian mass in a postmenopausal woman carries a high probability of malignancy. In menstruating women endometriosis should be considered.

3.6 ULTRASOUND EVALUATION OF ADNEAXAL MASSES

An ultrasound examination is the most valuable diagnostic study in the evaluation of an adnexal or pelvic mass. Although operator dependent, an experienced ultrasonographer should be able to determine the size and complexity of the mass.

The size of a normal ovary varies throughout a woman's life, with a normal ovary measuring 3.5 X 2 X 1.5 cm in the premenopausal patient and 1.5 X 0.7 X 0.5 cm two to five years after menopause. A postmenopausal ovary twice the size of the contralateral one is considered a suspicious finding. Ultrasound can also indicate whether a mass is cystic or solid, whether its contour is smooth or contains excrescences, and whether it contains any internal septa or papillae. Each of the latter characteristics is suggestive of malignancy. The presence of ascites also may indicate a malignant process.

3.7 MANAGEMENT OF ADNEXAL MASSES

Once a mass has been detected and evaluated by ultrasound and serum tumor markers, the physician is faced with the dilemma of how best to manage an individual patient. The questions to be answered are which patients can be safely followed, which should be operated on immediately and which can be evaluated laparoscopically. Again, the age of the patient and the results of the work-up are important in determining appropriate management. Detection of an adnexal mass in a premenarchal patient warrants prompt ultrasound evaluation and referral. As mentioned previously, ovarian cysts in prepubertal girls after the first few weeks of life are abnormal and likely to be neoplastic.

Figure 1: Management scheme for an adnexal mass in the premenopausal patient (Drake, 1998)

Figure II: Management of ovarian cysts in postmenopausal women (Drake, 1998)

CHAPTER FOUR

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

4.1 RESEARCH DESIGN

This prospective study consisted of 480 subjects with adnexal masses out of which 392 subjects were followed up with histopathology tests and serial rescans between May, 2008 and April, 2010. The ages of the subjects range between 5 years and 64years. The size and sonographic patterns of any detected adnexal masses were observed and noted.

4.2 POPULATION

The population for the study include all referrals for pelvic sonography (20,015 in number) at the Eko hospitals in Lagos State within the period of the study.

4.21 INCLUSION CRITERIA

1. All patients that present with clinical palpable adnexal masses
2. All patients referred to the department with pelvic pain whom on scanning revealed an adnexal mass
3. Patients bleeding per-vagina who on scan revealed adnexal mass
4. Patients with incidentally detected masses in the adnexae
5. Patients with Pedunculated/subserous Fibroids.

4.22 EXCLUSION CRITERIA

Subjects were excluded from the study:

1. If the patient with imperforate hymen needs to have a transvaginal scan because of equivocal findings on transabdominal scan
2. If the patient is Pregnant with history of premature rupture of membranes and needs to have a transvaginal scan because of equivocal findings on transabdominal scan.

4.3 SAMPLE SIZE

480 subjects were recruited in this prospective study but the sample size of 392 was determined using the formula:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2} \text{ (Yamane Taro 1973)}$$

Where 'n' is the sample size, 'N' is the population and 'e' is the accepted tolerance error of 0.05

4.4 SAMPLING PROCEDURE

The sampling technique used was convenience and purposive sampling. This means that any subject that was referred to the department for pelvic ultrasonography and met the inclusion criteria was used for the study until the required number was obtained.

4.5 EQUIPMENT USED

All the patients were scanned in with Siemens Sonoline – 1 real time scanner equipped with 3.5MHZ sector and 5MHZ linear array transducers (serial no-PE90760). Incorporated in the equipment was digital frame memory with video output, selectable transmitting focus, dynamic receiving focus, and facilities for pre- and post processing of data. It had a programmable Time Gain Compensator (TGC) adjustment which allows for proper contrast adjustments. The equipment has a versatile caliper system and user programmable biometric tables for documentation of data as well as an automatic system data display inserts (for positioning of texts and notations) and a specific protocol mode for varying applications.

4.6 DATA COLLECTON

The sonographic patterns of adnexal masses in 392 subjects that met the inclusion criteria were studied between May 2008 and April 2010.

4.7 SCANNING TECHNIQUE

All patients were required to drink one litre of water, an hour prior to the scan to fill the urinary bladder and provide acoustic window for optimal visualization of the adnexae.

Adequate amount of ultrasound coupling gel was applied to the skin before the

scan to remove air bubbles between the skin and the probe and to promote adequate coupling and transmission of sound. The mass is then studied in detail with angled and additional scans.

Serial longitudinal and transverse projection of the pelvic organs were obtained. Measurement of any identified adnexal mass was made using the in-built electronic callipers. The pelvis of each subject was scanned and adnexal masses present were identified and measured. Length of the mass was obtained by measuring the longest diameter through the mass. The masses were categorized as cystic, complex or solid. Most of the cystic masses were required to come back for a rescan for follow up assessment. Equivocal findings on transabdominal study were further evaluated using endovaginal sonography. Where indicated, liver, Para-aortic nodes, kidneys and other areas such as Morrison's pouch were scanned to rule out metastases.

4.71 IMAGES

Fig IV: Showing a Left adnaxal complex mass possibly a tubo – ovarian abscess

Fig V ; Showing a complex multiseptated cystic adnexal mass possibly a cystadenoma.

Fig vi : showing a left adnexal cystic mass and a right adnexal mass.

Fig vii: showing a left ovarian cystic mass

Fig VIII: showing a right adnexal complex cystic mass possibly a haemorrhagic cyst

4.8

DATA ANALYSIS

Adnexal masses were classified into three major groups using their sonographic appearances. All echo free adnexal masses with thick or thin walls and without internal echoes were grouped as cystic, while those with internal echoes /solid components were classified as complex masses. Masses that contain homogenous/heterogenous echoes with or without calcification were grouped as solid masses.

Detailed reports of the adnexal masses were documented. Each subject was followed up with the referring gynaecologist/physician to document the management procedure that was embarked on by the clinical team. Out of the 480 subjects, we were able to follow up 392 subjects; 172 went for laparotomy and excision of the mass which were sent for histopathology while the remaining 220 subjects were considered innocuous and undeserving of surgery and thus were only followed up with serial scans. The sonographic findings were matched with the results of histopathology tests to confirm the sonographic diagnoses. The correlation/regression analysis and signal detection theory were used to analyze the data while the chi- squared (χ^2) test of independence was used to test the hypothesis.

4.81 TABLE II SHOWING SIGNAL DETECTION THEORY VALUES FOR SONOGRAPHY DIAGNOSES AND HISTOPATHOLOGY /RESCAN DIAGNOSES

	NUMBER OF HISTOPATHOLOGY / RESCAN DIAGNOSES	
Number of Sonography Diagnoses	+	-
+	28 (TP)	29 (FP)
-	4 (FN)	331 (TN)

4.82 TABLE III SHOWING SIGNAL DETECTION THEORY VALUES FOR SONOGRAPHY DIAGNOSES AND HISTOPATHOLOGY DIAGNOSES ONLY

	NUMBER OF HISTOPATHOLOGY DIAGNOSES	
Number of Sonography Diagnoses	+	-
+	28 (TP)	29 (FP)
-	4 (FN)	111 (TN)

4.83 FORMULAE

- i. Sensitivity = $\frac{TP}{TP + FN}$
- ii. Specificity = $\frac{TN}{TN + FP}$
- iii. Positive predictive value = $\frac{TP}{TP + FP}$

$$\text{iv. Negative predictive value} = \frac{\text{TN}}{\text{TN} + \text{FN}}$$

$$\text{v. Accuracy} = \frac{\text{TP} + \text{TN}}{\text{TOTAL}}$$

Where:

- TP = True Positive
 TN = True Negative
 FP = False Positive
 FN = False Negative
 vi. $X^2 = \sum \frac{(O - e)^2}{e}$

Where

- X^2 = Chi – squared value
 O = Observed value
 e = Expected value

TABLE IV SHOWING OBSERVED AND EXPECTED X^2 FREQUENCIES

DIAGNOSES	INITIAL SONOGRAPHY DIAGNOSES			Total
	Benign Adnexal Masses	Malignant adnexal Masses	Follow up	
Confirmed by Histopathology/ Rescan	108 (103)	28 (50)	212 (195)	348
Not confirmed by Histopathology/ Rescan	8 (13)	28 (6)	8 (25)	44
Total	116	56	220	392

4.9 COMMENTS ON RESULT

Four hundred and eighty subjects aged between 5 to 65years underwent ultrasound

scan in this prospective study to characterize their adnexal masses (Table V). Ultrasound diagnoses in 86% (412/480) of the subjects revealed benign adnexal masses predominantly among premenopausal women between the ages of 35 and 44 years while 14% (64/480) of the subjects had malignant adnexal masses (Table V). The adnexal masses were categorized into three (Table VI) namely: Simple Cystic Masses (42.5%), Complex Cystic Masses (50%) and Solid Masses (7.5%).

Out of the 204 subjects with definitive Sonography diagnoses of simple cystic masses, 172 subjects (84%) had Follicular Cystic Masses whereas 32 subjects (16%) had Corpus Luteum Cystic Masses (Table VII). Among the simple cystic masses, follicular cysts were very common. The definitive Sonography diagnoses in 240 subjects with Complex Adnexal Masses (Table VIII) showed 64 Malignant adnexal Masses (27%), 4 Endometriomas (2%), 28 Ectopic Pregnancies (12%), 64 Pelvic Inflammatory Diseases (27%) and 80 other benign adnexal masses (33%)

Transabdominal/Transvaginal studies in 36 subjects with solid masses (Table IX) showed 4 Pelvic Kidneys (11%) and 32 Pedunculated Fibroids (89%). Benign adnexal masses are the most common complex adnexal masses in the population. Table X shows all the adnexal masses (simple, complex and solid adnexal masses) along with their percentage distribution. Endometriomas (0.8%) and pelvic kidneys (0.8%) are the least common adnexal masses in the population.

Following the initial definitive Sonography diagnoses in 480 subjects, 212 (44%)

were referred for Laparotomy while 268 (56%) were referred for Follow-up rescans by the referring gynaecologist respectively. Out of the 212 subjects with definitive Sonography diagnoses (Table XI) of endometriomas, ectopic pregnancies, pedunculated fibroids, pelvic inflammatory diseases, benign and malignant adnexal masses, 172 (81%) subjects reported and underwent laparotomy while 40 subjects did not report for laparotomy. Masses identified during laparotomy were excised and sent for histopathology test. Out of the 172 subjects that went for laparotomy, 136 (79%) subjects had histopathology diagnoses that matched with initial sonography diagnoses (fig. XI). Sonography diagnoses in 21% (36/172) of the subjects followed up with histopathology tests were erroneous (Table XIII). Histopathology revealed these masses to include 4 ruptured ovarian cysts and 4 mucinous adenocarcinomas diagnosed by Sonography as ectopic pregnancies and benign unilocular cystic masses respectively. Others include 28 masses diagnosed by Sonography as malignant which were found to be benign ovarian masses by histopathology. They include 6 benign cystic teratomas and 2 adenofibromas (misdiagnosed as malignant ovarian masses), 10 endometriomas (misdiagnosed as borderline mucinous neoplasms), 9 mucinous cystadenomas (misdiagnosed as malignant cystic masses), and one broad ligament fibroid earlier diagnosed as a sarcoma by Sonography. The Scatterplot and Regression line (fig X) showed a strong positive correlation between initial

sonography and histopathology diagnoses ($r = 0.93$). Compared with histopathology diagnoses alone, the accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, positive and negative predictive values (PPV and NPV) of initial sonography diagnoses were 81%, 88%, 79%, 49%, 97% respectively. Initial Sonography reports made correct diagnoses in 79% and 88% benign and malignant adnexal masses respectively. A model for predicting the accuracy of initial Sonography diagnoses is given by the simple regression function; $Y = 0.732x + 1.682$ ($r^2 = 0.834$, $0.0109 \leq P < 0.05$). The clinical significance of this model is explained by the coefficient of determination ($r^2 = 83\%$). Out of 268 subjects with definitive Sonography diagnoses of simple ovarian cystic masses, pelvic inflammatory diseases and pelvic kidneys, 220 (82%) subjects reported and underwent follow up rescans (Table XI) while 48 (18%) subjects did not report for follow up rescans. Out of the 220 subjects that underwent follow up rescans, 212 (96%) subjects had rescan diagnoses that matched initial sonography diagnoses. The scatterplot and Regression line (figure IX) shows a strong positive correlation between sonography and rescan diagnoses ($r = 0.99$). A model for predicting the accuracy of initial Sonography diagnoses is given by the simple regression function; $Y = 0.951x + 0.893$ ($r^2 = 0.999$, $0.0056 \leq P < 0.05$). For subjects that underwent histopathology tests/rescans, the accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, positive and negative predictive values (PPV and NPV) of initial sonography diagnoses were 92%, 88%, 92%, 49%, 99% respectively. The

scatterplot (fig XIII) showed a strong positive correlation between initial sonography and histopathology/rescan diagnoses ($r = 0.99$). In general, Sonography made correct diagnoses in 93% (336/360) and 88% (28/32) benign and malignant adnexal masses respectively. An overall model for predicting the accuracy of initial Sonography diagnoses is given by the simple regression function; $Y = 0.941x - 2.340$ ($r^2 = 0.974$, $7.8278 \times 10^{-7} \leq P < 0.05$). The overall measure of the clinical significance of this model is given by the coefficient of determination (r^2) = 97% i.e. 97% of the total variations in the histopathology/rescan diagnoses is explained by variations in the sonography diagnoses while 2.6% of the variations in the histopathology/rescan diagnoses is attributed to the influence of other factors not explained by the regression equation (coefficient of non-determination, $1 - r^2 = 0.026$). Analysis of the initial three categories of adnexal masses and their eventual outcome after being subjected to laparotomy/histopathology and rescan (Table XIV) showed that in 172 (96%) out of 180 subjects diagnosed as having simple ovarian cystic masses by sonography, the masses resolved and the ovaries returned to their normal sizes after 4 weeks of follow up rescan in keeping with the standard procedure with unilocular echo-free cysts < 50 mm in diameter (Ekerhoved et al., 2001) but the size of the 8 masses in the remaining 8 (4%) subjects persisted and continued to increase in size with the largest mean transverse diameter measuring 62mm in size after 6 weeks of follow

up rescans. The subjects were referred for laparotomy and histopathology confirmed the masses as benign ovarian cysts. Out of 191 subjects with complex adnexal masses followed up with sonography and histopathology / rescan, the size of 36 (18%) PIDS resolved progressively on follow up rescans with reabsorption of pouch of douglas fluid following a course of antibiotics (table XII). Histopathology revealed the remaining 155 (82%) complex adnexal masses as follows; 24 ectopic pregnancies, 32 malignant ovarian masses, 4 PIDs, 81 benign ovarian masses and 14 endometriomas (table XIV). Out of 21 Solid adnexal masses followed up with sonography and histopathology or rescan, 4 (19%) subjects had pelvic kidneys by follow up rescans while 16 pedunculated fibroids and 1 broad ligament fibroid were confirmed by histopathology in 17 (81%) subjects respectively (Table XIV). Laparotomy/Histopathology diagnoses revealed that the adnexal masses in 75% (135 / 180) of the subjects followed up with laparotomy and histopathology tests were located in the ovary. They include 103 benign ovarian tumours and 32 malignant ovarian neoplasms. Extra ovarian masses (24 ectopic pregnancies, 4 endometriotic cysts and 16 pedunculated fibroids and 1 broad ligament fibroid) were confirmed in 45 subjects.

4.91 LIST OF TABLES

Table II: Showing signal detection theory values for sonography diagnoses and histopathology diagnoses/rescan

- Table III: Showing signal detection theory values for sonography diagnoses and histopathology diagnoses only.
- Table IV: Showing observed and expected χ^2 frequencies.
- Table V: Age distribution of the adnexal masses
- Table VI: Analysis of transabdominal/transvaginal categorization of the adnexal masses in 480 subjects
- Table VII: Table showing analysis of definitive ultrasound diagnoses in 180 subjects with simple cystic masses.
- Table VIII: Table showing analysis of definitive ultrasound diagnoses in 240 subjects with complex adnexal masses.
- Table IX: Table showing analysis of definitive ultrasound diagnoses in 36 subjects with solid adnexal masses .
- Table X: Analysis of recategorized adnexal masses based on TAS/TVS definitive diagnoses
- Table XI: Table showing number of subjects that were subjected to laparotomy/histopathological diagnoses and rescans
- TABLE XII: Masses that were followed up with serial sonograms
- TABLE XIII: Correlation between sonography diagnoses and histopathology diagnoses.
- TABLE XIV: Initial sonography diagnoses compared with final histopathological diagnoses / follow – up rescan.
- Table XV: Age distribution of the adnexal masses before and after Histopathology/ Rescan diagnoses

4.92 LIST OF FIGURES

- Figure IX: A diagram showing the linear regression line and scatter diagram for sonography/ rescan diagnoses
- Figure X: Showing the linear regression line and the scatter diagram for sonography/histopathology diagnoses

Figure XI: Pie chart showing the correlation between sonography diagnoses and histopathology diagnoses

Figure XII: Pie chart showing the percentage distribution of the adnexal masses in the population

Figure XIII: Showing the linear regression line and the scatter diagram for sonography and histopathology /rescan diagnoses

TABLE V**AGE DISTRIBUTION OF THE ADNEXAL MASSES**

S/N	Age (Years)	Number of Benign adnexal masses by sonography	Number of malignant adnexal masses by sonography	Total
1	5 -14	4	0	4
2	15 – 24	60	0	60
3	25 – 34	128	0	128
4	35 – 44	182	18	200
5	45 – 54	27	21	48
6	55 – 64	15	25	40
	Total	412	64	480

TABLE VI
ANALYSIS OF TRANSABDOMINAL/TRANSVAGINAL
CATEGORIZATION OF THE ADNEXAL MASSES IN 480 SUBJECTS.

S/N	CATEGORIES	NO OF SUBJECTS	PERCENTAGE
1.	Simple cystic masses	204	42.5%
2.	Complex cystic masses	240	50%
3.	Solid masses	36	7.5%
TOTAL		480	100%

TABLE VII: TABLE SHOWING ANALYSIS OF DEFINITIVE
ULTRASOUND DIAGNOSES IN 180 SUBJECTS WITH SIMPLE CYSTIC
MASSES.

S/N	Simple cystic masses	No of subjects	%
1.	Follicular cysts	172	84%
2	Corpus luteum cyst	32	16%
TOTAL		204	100%

TABLE VIII
TABLE SHOWING ANALYSIS OF DEFINITIVE SONOGRAPHY
DIAGNOSES IN 240 SUBJECTS WITH COMPLEX ADNEXAL MASSES.

S/N	Complex masses	No of subjects	Percentage
1.	Benign Ovarian Masses	80	33%
2.	Malignant Ovarian Masses	64	27%
3.	Endometriomas	4	2%
4.	Ectopic Pregnancies	28	12%
5.	PID	64	27%
TOTAL		240	100%

TABLE IX

TABLE SHOWING ANALYSIS OF DEFINITIVE SONOGRAPHY
DIAGNOSES IN 36 SUBJECTS WITH SOLID ADNEXAL MASSES

S/N	Solid Masses	No of Subjects	Percentage
1.	Pelvic Kidneys	4	11%
2.	Pedunculated Fibroids	32	89%
TOTAL		36	5%

TABLE X**ANALYSIS OF RECATEGORIZED ADNEXAL MASSES BASED ON TAS/TVS DEFINITIVE DIAGNOSES**

S/N	TAS/TVS DEFINITIVE DIAGNOSES	NO OF SUBJECTS THAT UNDERWENT TAS/± TVS	PERCENTAGE
1	Simple ovarian cystic masses	204	42.5
2.	Endometrioma	4	0.8
3.	Pedunculated Fibroid	32	6.7
4.	Pelvic inflammatory diseases	64	13.3
5.	Benign Ovarian Masses	80	16.7
6.	Malignant Ovarian Masses	64	13.3
7.	Pelvic Kidney	4	0.8
8.	Ectopic Pregnancy	28	5.8
TOTAL		480	100%

TABLE XI**TABLE SHOWING NUMBER OF SUBJECTS THAT WERE SUBJECTED TO LAPARATOMY/HISTOPATHOLOGICAL DIAGNOSES AND RESCAN**

S/N	TAS/TVS Definitive Diagnoses	No of Subjects that underwent TAS/± TVS	No of subject that underwent Laparotomy/ Histopathology Diagnoses	No of subjects that underwent Follow up rescan	No of Absconment
1	Simple ovarian cystic masses	204	-	180	24
2.	Endometrioma	4	4	-	-
3.	Pedunculated Fibroid	32	16	-	16
4.	Pelvic inflammatory diseases	64	4	36	24
5.	Benign Ovarian Masses	80	64	-	16
6.	Malignant Ovarian Masses	64	56	-	8
7.	Pelvic Kidney	4	-	4	
8.	Ectopic Pregnancy	28	28	-	-
TOTAL		480	172 (35.8%)	220 (45.8%)	88 (18.3%)

TABLE XII**MASSES THAT WERE FOLLOWED UP WITH SERIAL SONOGRAMS**

Sonography Diagnoses (TAS/TVS)	No of Subjects Followed up by Rescan	No. confirmed by Rescan	Outcome of Rescan
Simple adnexal cystic masses	180 (82%)	172	The Masses Resolved and the ovaries returned to normal sizes after 2 – 4 weeks of rescan. 8 unilateral adnexal cystic masses from 8 subjects persisted and continued to increase in size after 6 weeks of follow up rescan. The subjects were referred for laparotomy by the referring physician. Evidence at histopathology confirmed benign ovarian cystic masses.
Pelvic Kidney	4 (2%)	4	Pelvic kidney confirmed by observing dilated pelvic – calyceal system in the LT iliac fossa in a hydrating subject
PID	36 (16%)	36	Masses resolved gradually on re-scan with re-absorption of Pouch of Douglas fluid following a course of antibiotics
TOTAL	220	212	

FIG. IX: SHOWING THE LINEAR REGRESSION LINE AND SCATTER DIAGRAM FOR SONOGRAPHY/ RESCAN DIAGNOSES

TABLE XIII**CORRELATION BETWEEN SONOGRAPHY DIAGNOSES AND HISTOPATHOLOGY DIAGNOSES**

S/N	Sonography Diagnoses TAS/±TVS	Subjects Followed up with Laparotomy/histopathology	No of Sonography Diagnoses confirmed by Laparotomy/histopathology	Erroneous sonography Diagnoses	Total number identified by Laparotomy /Histopathology
1.	Ectopic Pregnancies	28	24	4	24
2.	Fibroids	16	16	NIL	17
3.	Malignant Ovarian masses	56	28	28	32
4.	PIDs	4	4	NIL	4
5.	Benign Ovarian Masses	64	60	4	81
6.	Endometriomas	4	4	NIL	14
TOTAL		172	136 (79%)	36 (21%)	172

FIG X: SHOWING THE LINEAR REGRESSION LINE AND THE SCATTER DIAGRAM FOR SONOGRAPHY /HISTOPATHOLOGY DIAGNOSES

Fig XI – Pie chart Showing the Correlation between Sonography Diagnoses and Histopathology Test

INITIAL SONOGRAPHY DIAGNOSES COMPARED WITH FINAL HISTOPATHOLOGICAL DIAGNOSES / FOLLOW – UP RESCAN

INITIAL SONOGRAPHY DIAGNOSES	NO OF INITIAL SONOGRAPHY DIAGNOSES	RESULT OF RESCAN	HISTOPATHOLOGY DIAGNOSES
Simple adnexal Cystic Masses	180 (46%)	172(96%) were simple (functional)cysts.8 (4%) masses were referred for histopathology	8 (4%) benign ovarian cystic masses
Complex Cystic Masses	191 (49%)	36 (18%) PIDs	155 (82%) ; namely 24 ectopic pregnancies, 32 malignant ovarian masses, 4 Pelvic Inflammatory Diseases, 81 Benign Ovarian Masses and 14 endometriomas .
Solid masses	21 (5%)	4(19%) pelvic kidney	16 pedunculated fibroids and 1 broad ligament fibroid (81%)
TOTAL	392	212 (55%)	180 (45%)

Figure XII – Pie chart showing the percentage distribution of the adnexal masses in the population

FIG XIII: SHOWING THE LINEAR REGRESSION LINE AND THE SCATTER DIAGRAM FOR SONOGRAPHY AND HISTOPATHOLOGY /RESCAN DIAGNOSES

TABLE XV
AGE DISTRIBUTION OF THE ADNEXAL MASS BEFORE AND AFTER
HISTOPATHOLOGY/ RESCAN DIAGNOSES

S/N	Age (Years)	No. of Benign adnexal masses by initial sonography Diagnoses	No. confirmed by histopathol ogy/Rescan	No. of malignant masses by sonography Diagnoses	No. of malignant adnexal masses confirmed by histopathology/ Rescan	Total
1	5 -14	4	4	0	0	4
2	15 – 24	43	43	0	0	43
3	25 – 34	111	111	0	0	111
4	35 – 44	139	147	16	8	155
5	45 – 54	19	27	18	10	37
6	55 – 64	20	28	22	14	42
	Total	336 (86%)	360(92%)	56 (14%)	32	392

4.93 TEST OF HYPOTHESIS

H_0 : There is no significant difference between sonographic diagnosis of adnexal pathology and the definitive diagnosis provided by histopathology test/follow up rescan.

H_1 : There is a significant difference between the sonographic diagnosis of adnexal pathology and the definitive diagnosis provided by histopathology test/follow up rescan.

Calculated Chi – Squared value = $\chi^2 = 3.56$

Critical Value of Chi Squares = $\chi^2_{0.05} = 5.991$

Since the calculated Chi-squared value (χ^2) is less than the Critical value at the 5% level of significance, and falls within the acceptance region ($0.9 \leq P > 0.05$), we therefore reject H_1 and accept H_0 i.e. there is no significant difference between Sonographic diagnosis of Adnexal Pathology and Histopathology test/ follow up Rescan.

5.0 DISCUSSION & CONCLUSION

5.1 DISCUSSION

Several attempts have been made to distinguish ovarian malignancy from questionable ovarian lesions on the basis of grey scale ultrasound and or colour Doppler features (Kurjak et al., 1993). In the present study, grey-scale ultrasound was used to characterize adnexal masses in 392 subjects using the results of histopathology and serial rescans as gold standards.

5.12 ACCURACY OF SONOGRAPHY IN THE DIAGNOSES OF ADNEXAL MASSES.

In the present study, Sonography made correct diagnoses in 100% of all functional ovarian cystic masses but obtained a correlation of 96% (212/220) in the diagnoses of simple adnexal cysts. Accurate diagnoses (100%) of functional cysts have been reported in a related study (Satoskar, 1991) using transabdominal sonography.

Also, there is 86% correlation between the result of ultrasonography and histopathology in the diagnoses of ectopic pregnancy compared to a correlation of 97% obtained in a related study (Bruno et al., 2005). The slightly higher accuracy obtained in the later study is attributed to the combined use of sonography and serum hCG levels to identify early ectopic pregnancies which will have been hitherto undetected by sonography (Birte et al., 2009). In the present study, a combination of sonographic patterns namely a complex adnexal mass adjacent to an enlarged empty uterus, a pseudogestational sac with single echogenic rim, echogenic (haemorrhagic) free fluid in the pouch of Douglas (Leung,2001) were

used to obtain diagnostic results in 24 out of 28 subjects. This gave an erroneous diagnoses of only 14% slightly higher than 11.3% obtained in a related study (Mansoor et al., 2003). Therefore, in the present study, Grey scale ultrasonography is very important in reducing the maternal morbidity and mortality associated with ectopic pregnancy. The later findings has been collaborated by another related study (Omole-Ohonsi, 2008). Laparatomy/histopathology revealed that all the ectopic gestational sacs were located in the fallopian tube.

Moreover, the correlation between sonography and histopathology in the diagnoses of fibroids in the region of the adnexae was 94% (16 out of 17).The erroneous diagnoses during sonography was that of a broad ligament fibroid (confirmed by laparatomy and histopathology) earlier diagnosed as sarcoma by sonography. Another related study had reported that some pedunculated fibroids can develop long tenous stalk and adhere to the surrounding structures such as the broad ligament (Hsu – chong yeh, 1999). According to the later study, such fibroids may loose their original attatchment to uterus and may mimic an ovarian tumour (as reported by sonography in the present study). One of the reasons why the pedicle connecting the leiomyoma to the uterus was not demonstrated during sonography in the present study can be attributed to the fact that the pedicle may have moved

out of the true pelvis during scan (Hsu Chong Yeh, 1999).The other reason is that sonography is limited in its field of view and therefore unable to view the

relationship of the pedunculated fibroid and the uterus (Maria et al., 2006;Theera Tongsong et al., 2006). On the other hand, the former study (Hsu – Chong Yeh., 1999) also reported that the pedicle can be demonstrated by using transducer pressure to separate the uterus and the pedunculated leiomyoma thereby imaging the pedicle or using Colour Doppler sonography to demonstrate the vessels within the pedicle to further confirm the diagnosis of pedunculated fibroid. On the contrary, other related studies opined that the later approach can be misleading because some fibroids have high diastolic arterial waveforms similar to some ovarian cancers and therefore advocated the use of transvaginal sonography (Okoye, 2000) or MRI (Susanna et al., 2006) to image the pedicle and definitive characterization respectively.

The least correlation (29%) 4/14 recorded in this study between sonography and histopathology was in the diagnoses of endometriomas. In the present study, 71% (10/14) of the endometriomas were missed (wrongly diagnosed as borderline mucinous neoplasms) during sonography because endometriod cysts of the ovaries presented as hypoechoic cystic masses containing low level echoes mimicking borderline ovarian neoplasms. This had been collaborated in related studies which reported that ultrasonographic features of endometriomas were variable and can

mimic those of other benign and malignant ovarian lesions (Paula et al.,2001; Elizabeth et al.,2007) and therefore less sensitive than MRI (91%) in the diagnoses of most endometriomas (susanna et al., 2006).

The initial sonography diagnoses matched the histopathology diagnoses in 79% (136/172) of the subjects that underwent Laparotomy/Histopathology tests which is slightly higher than 74.6% correct diagnoses obtained in a related study (Satoskar, 1991) using transabdominal sonography. The slightly higher correlation obtained in this study was attributed to the use of transvaginal ultrasound to confirm equivocal findings on transabdominal scan. There is a strong positive correlation between sonography and histopathology diagnoses ($r = 0.91$, figure XI). Also, there is strong positive correlation between Sonography and Rescan diagnoses ($r = 0.99$, figure IX).

The accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, negative predictive value (NPV) and positive predictive value (PPV) of initial sonography diagnoses compared with histopathology diagnoses alone in the diagnoses of adnexal masses were 81%,88%,79%,97% and 49% respectively. NPV of 97% and PPV of 50% have also been reported in a related study (Stein et al., 1995) but the PPV of 49% obtained in this study is low compared to 76.6% obtained in another related study (Madan et al., 2004). The use of combined sonomorphological and vascular scoring (obtained by the use of colour and spectral Doppler) accounts for the

marked difference in the PPV between the present study and the later. There is also strong positive correlation between sonography and histopathology / rescan diagnoses ($r = 0.99$, figure XII). An overall model for predicting the accuracy of sonography diagnoses is given by the simple regression function $Y = 0.941x - 2.340$ ($r^2 = 0.974$, $p = 7.8278 \times 10^{-7}$). The addition of the initial sonography findings in subjects that later underwent follow up rescans to the definitive sonography diagnoses in subjects that underwent histopathology tests did not have any effect on the sensitivity (88%) and PPV (49%) but increased the specificity (from 79% to 92%), NPV (from 97% to 99%) and accuracy (from 81% to 92%) respectively. The significance of the high NPV (99%) and low PPV (49%) in the present study is that grey scale sonography is reliable in the prediction of benignity of an adnexal mass (Yong-Yeon et al., 2000) but not reliable in the prediction of malignancy of an adnexal mass (stein et al., 1995; kupesic, 2006). However, the accuracy of sonography in the correct diagnosis of malignancy in the present study is good (88%) 28/32 similar to 89% obtained in a similar study (Satoska et al., 1991) using transabdominal sonography. Hence, follow up rescans is appropriate (ekerhoved et al., 2001) and increases the confidence for which an accurate diagnosis of benignity can be made especially for functional ovarian cysts. Similar diagnostic parameters with respect to sensitivity (88%), specificity (97%) and accuracy (95%) has been reported in a related study (Buy et al., 1996). The slightly

higher diagnostic accuracy obtained in the later study is attributed to the use of colour Doppler Sonography in addition to conventional sonography in the characterization of the adnexal masses although other related studies has posited that the use of colour Doppler ultrasound rarely change the impression made from grey scale sonographic findings but only increases the confidence with which a correct diagnosis is made (Lisa et al., 1999; valentine 1999). On the contrary, the present study agrees with the findings of related studies which insist that the addition of color Doppler to conventional sonography produced a specificity and positive predictive values higher than those of conventional sonography alone (Buy et al., 1999) and could probably add relevant information to the differential diagnosis between benign and malignant adnexal masses (Enrico et al., 2005; Sladkevicius et al., 2007).

Furthermore, one of the factors that contributed to diagnostic errors during sonography in this study was that papillary projections which were considered as a strong sign of malignancy (Juan et al.,2007) were also present in 2 benign adenofibromas (earlier diagnosed as malignant ovarian masses by sonography). Sonographic appearances of papillary projections have been reported to be present in benign tumours (Douglas et al., 2010) and their presence in this study explains some of the false positive ultrasound diagnosis of malignancy. The difficulties in making correct diagnoses in the present study can also be attributed to the limited

field of view (maria et al., 2006) and limited diagnostic ability of grey scale ultrasound (Kupesic, 2000) which have been reported to account for the overlap of ultrasound imaging features of some benign and malignant ovarian masses (Lee, 2001; madan et al.,2004). As a result advanced multi-parameter analysis including the use of contrast enhanced power Doppler imaging (Henri marret et al., 2004) or three dimensional power Doppler vascular network assessment of adnexal masses (Juan et al., 2008) which were lacking in the present study has also been reported to precisely aid in discriminating malignant from benign adnexal masses.

5.13 PATTERN OF OCCURRENCE OF THE ADNEXAL MASSES

Ninety two percent (360/392) of the subjects had benign adnexal masses which makes them the commonest adnexal masses in the studied population while 8% (32/392) of the subjects had malignant adnexal masses (table XV). Similar findings has been reported in related studies (Timmerman et al., 2008). Another related study had reported more malignant ovarian masses (74.4%) than benign tumours (16%) contrary to the findings of this study (Christopher et al., 2008). The high percentage of malignant adnexal masses in the later study compared to the present study is attributed to the fact that the later study was narrowed only to postmenopausal women which are at greater risk of ovarian malignancies (Tanos

et al., 1994). Table XIV shows that the common benign adnexal masses among the subjects in this study were complex adnexal cystic masses (49%) followed by simple cystic masses (46%). They include functional cysts (44%), benign ovarian masses (21%), hydrosalpinx, pyosalpinx and tubo-ovarian abscesses resulting from pelvic inflammatory diseases (10%). With respect to age, the benign adnexal masses were common among premenopausal women between the ages of 35 and 44 while malignant adnexal masses were common among postmenopausal women above 45 years of age (table XV). This has been corroborated by (Eugene et al., 2001) who opined that Postmenopausal status correlates significantly with the probability ($P = 0.002$) of malignancy.

Finally, the prevalence of cancer resulting from an adnexal mass in the population was 8% (fig XII) which corresponds exactly to the estimate proposed for unilocular cysts (Granberg et al., 1989), but similar to 7.6% obtained in another related study (Enrico et al., 2005). The slightly lower prevalence of adnexal cancer obtained in the later study compared to the present study might be explained from the design of the study which included only small adnexal masses and excluded large ovarian carcinomas (included in the present study) often observed in postmenopausal subjects (Sohaib et al., 2003).

5.2 CONCLUSION

Grey scale Ultrasonography is valuable in the diagnoses of adnexal masses

5.3 AREAS OF FURTHER RESEARCH

1. Evaluation of adnexal masses using Color Doppler Imaging
2. The use of ultrasound in the diagnosis of pelvic masses

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